

A Quantitative Study of Tornadoes in South America

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Abstract

This article aims to develop a quantitative study about tornado events in South America, in order to create a database to verify the locations that have suffered the most from the phenomenon and dedicated to the study of the subject. The information for carrying out such research was compiled from articles cited in Google Scholar (or Google Scholar), covering the period from 1985 to 2018. For the search, keywords such as “tornado” (in Portuguese), “tormenta de viento” (in Spanish) and “tornado” (in English). During the survey, the locations (city, country), the number of deaths and injuries, and the estimated speed were noted. Speed was based on the Enhanced Fujita Scale (EF), when this was not described in the body of the text, photos and descriptions of the destruction were analyzed to infer them. The results showed that there was a concentration regarding the phenomenon mainly in the “southeastern region of South America”, and another region comprising Colombia and Venezuela, close to the coast of the Caribbean Sea. Brazil reported the highest number of events in the period (247), while Argentina and Uruguay had the most aggressive events (EF-4). Spring and summer are the most opportune seasons for the development of supercell clouds, similar to what happens in Tornado Alley.

Keywords: Thunderstorm, Tornado, Supercell, South America, Fujita Scale.

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1. Introduction

Tornadoes occur in places conducive to the development of large storms. The tornado is a natural atmospheric meteorological phenomenon, being one of the most violent. These differ from other events such as hurricanes by size and formation process, since hurricanes only develop over the oceans and can last for several days. When a funnel cloud promotes surface circulation, it is called a tornado. They usually occur over continents, lasting a few minutes, causing great destruction [4, 6, 10, 15, 24].

They have been observed on all continents, except Antarctica. Some regions of the planet, due to their geographical position, concentrate a greater number of performances, as is the case of the tornado corridor in the United States of America, or also called “Tornado Alley”. However, it is possible that other countries are also constantly affected by tornadoes.

Quantitative recognition allows launching planning and organization strategies for the population that is sensitive to the action of these types of extreme meteorological events, having more time to take precautions against these disasters.

The process of formation of tornadoes is complex and has not been fully understood by science yet. But it is already known that supercell clouds are the main generator of such phenomena. According [6] the main characteristic of this type of cloud is the presence of the mesocyclone, a rotation inside the cloud. Part of this spin is caused by the Coriolis effects. Updrafts and downdrafts cause the mesocyclone to spin faster and longer [10].

2. Development

Thus, in 1971 Tetsuya Theodore Fujita, together with Alan Pearson, elaborated the Fujita Scale (from F-0, the weakest to F-5, the strongest).

However, due to the confusion of damage at higher scales (F-3, F-4 and F-5), the test was recalibrated to suit the different types of structures, this was attended by meteorologists and engineers and was developed in 2007, called the Improved Fujita Scale - EFM (or simply EF), shown in Figure (1).

The Enhanced Fujita Scale is the most commonly used in the US to estimate the speed of tornadoes. In the “Tornado Alley” region, an approximate

average of 1,000 events occur per year. Violent tornadoes (EF-4 and EF-5) account for only 1% of all cases, but are responsible for 67% of deaths in that country [23].

Figure 1: The Enhanced Fujita Scale with values in miles per hour and kilometers per hour (Rating 3 Second Gust (mph) 3 Second Gust (Km/h)).

EF SCALE		
Rating	3 Second Gust (mph)	3 Second Gust (Km/h)
EF-0	65-85	105-137
EF-1	86-110	138-177
EF-2	111-135	178-217
EF-3	136-165	218-265
EF-4	166-200	266-321
EF-5	over 200	over 321

Source: [25].

The EF scale is still a set of wind estimates (not measurements) based on damage. Uses three-second bursts estimated at point damage, based on a judgment of 8 levels of damage at 28 gauges. These estimates vary with height and exposure. Important: The 3 second gust is not the same wind as in standard surface observations. Standard measurements are taken by weather stations at open displays, using a directly measured speed of "one minute per mile" or 1.6 kilometers per hour [25].

The main explanation for a large number of these events in the United States is the meeting of the cold air masses of Canada, with the dry mass of the Rocky Mountains, and with the hot and humid one of the Gulf of Mexico [22, 23], associated to the emergence and rapid displacement of supercell clouds in the American Midwest with jet streams at altitude, causing wind shear.

The Enhanced Fujita Scale is the most commonly used in the US to estimate the speed of tornadoes. In the “Tornado Alley” region, an approximate average of 1,000 events occur per year. Violent tornadoes (EF-4 and EF-5) account for only 1% of all cases, but are responsible for 67% of deaths in that country [25].

Tornadoes are occasional in South America. The geographer Dyer was one of the first to study the passage of these phenomena by trails in satellite

images and aerial photogrammetry in south-central Brazil, Paraguay and northeastern Argentina, in the 60s and 70s [7]. The Figures (2, 3 and 4) below showed more examples these epics events in South America.

Figure 2: Tornado F-5 in San Justo (Argentina), Jan 10, 1973.

Source: [2].

Figure 3: Tornado EF-3 in Indaiatuba (Brazil), May 24, 2005.

Source: [11].

Figure 4: Tornado EF-4 in Dolores (Uruguay), Apr 15, 2016.

Source: [14].

The authors [16] demonstrated the preferential region of these events in South America and others such [4, 5, 15, 17, 20, 21, 24] described tornado episodes in several South American locations. There is also comment on the occurrence of a violent F-5 in San Justo, Argentina province of Santa Fe on January 10th 1973 [1], which left 70 dead and 350 injured, being considered the strongest of all the Southern Hemisphere of the planet.

Usually, tornadoes in the Southern Hemisphere rotate clockwise while in the Northern Hemisphere, tornadoes rotate counterclockwise, with the possible cause being the altitude jet at mid-latitudes [17, 25].

3. Methods

Having defined the spatial cut (South America), the time cut was chosen. According [3] the climate is a synthesis of successions of time, and a climatological normal of a place can be represented by a period of 30 to 35 years. Therefore, it was chosen to choose the years from the period 1985 to 2018 (34 years), because in addition to being a more recent period of the current work, it may represent a trend in the climatology of tornadoes in South America.

The Analytical Method was chosen for this research. This method is a path and also “a way of achieving a result by decomposing a phenomenon into its elements” [8] (p.17, our translation).

In the search for more reliable data to define the region where tornadoes occur, we searched for authors who cited phenomena in South America in Google Scholar (or Sci-Hub), whether with articles, book chapters, case studies, bibliographic reviews and other descriptions.

The starting point in Google Scholar was with the use of keywords, in Portuguese: “tornado”, “vendaval”; “tempestade”, “aguaceiros”, “inundações”, “furacão”, “ciclone”, “microexplosão”, “tormenta”, “nuvem funil”, “vendaval”, “tempestade severa” and “tromba d’água”. In Spanish: “tornado”, “tormenta de viento”, “huracan”, “ciclón”, “tormenta severa”, “viento”, “microtornados” and “tromba marina”. And also, in English: “tornado”, “twister”, “severe storm”, “microburst”, “hurricane”, “whirlwind”, “Funnel cloud” and “waterspout”. This is because such an event may have other nomenclatures, according to the local language. “Tornado” was

considered to be meteorological events with wind gyrations, being connected to a mother cloud (cumulonimbus) and over the continents. Waterspouts were not considered [22].

Several authors have written on the subject in South America [4, 5, 10, 17, 21], for example, in his works made a bibliographic historical survey, reporting more than 200 cases of tornadoes in Brazil from 1990 to 2010, and proposed a risk model of these events across Brazil. In this sense, [4] related such events with the use and occupation of the soil and, mainly, the topography. Described several actions in the state of Paraná (Brazil) [10, 17], while [21] described several tornadoes in Venezuela.

Some articles contained references and quotes from other works about new events, which were consulted. After that, all data were described in Excel spreadsheets, with the following information: location (city, department, state and country); hour; date; number of injured and dead; wind speed; damage; classification (F or EF). The number of citations of each case was chosen around the place of occurrence, verifying the level of importance that this event had repercussions among the others. With the grouped data, it was possible to elaborate the graphs and tables in order to make better use of the space and to make it easier to understand.

With the data, the ten most violent tornadoes in South America in this period were listed, initially taking into account the number of deaths, followed by the number of injuries and the classification on the EF scale. Finally, a brief discussion regarding these events with urbanized areas and socioeconomic damage.

4. Results

In total, 279 cases of tornadoes in South America were studied. However, it should be noted that 3 tornadoes had their distant displacements reaching neighboring cities. Among them, the following stand out: Marechal Cândido Rondon/Quatro Pontes on November 19th 2015, in Cafelândia/Nova Aurora on October 10th 2015 and Rosário do Ivaí/Rio Branco do Ivaí in 2017, both in the state of Paraná (Brazil) [10], totaling 276 valid tornadoes in the period 1985 to 2018.

It was found that Brazil is the most affected in South America, with 244 events, followed by Colombia with 12, Venezuela with 10, Argentina

with 8 and Uruguay, with 2. The other countries did not report cases. The sequence of Colombia and Venezuela was a novelty, as they are not part of the region delimited [6, 16]. From data mining, it was possible to group them in tables in Excel, gathering all event data by location (city, state and country) in South America, thus diagnosing the number of events on an annual basis, transcribed in Figure (5).

Figure 5: Annual base of tornadoes in South America from 1985 to 2018.

Source: The Authors.

From the results obtained, it can be seen that the year 2008 is the most representative in the annual relation, with 37 events. There is also a concentration of cases from 2004, 2005, and from 2007 to 2010 and another peak in 2015, all with more than 10 cases/year.

The years 1985, 1986, 1988, 1990 and 2018 did not report cases of tornadoes in South America in the period studied, so a "corridor" such as "Tornado Alley", where tornadoes occur regularly (around 1,000 per year), could not be considered. Still with the date data, the monthly occurrences of these events were listed, shown in figure 6.

The most representative month for tornado episodes was November and the least representative was August. In the months of September, October, November, and January, the advance of large convective systems over southeastern South America is common, such as Mesoscale Convective Complexes (MCCs) [19]. The month of May is more common the advance of Cold Fronts (FF) that trigger frontal convective

clouds. The month of August is generally marked by cold and dry air masses that block most of central South America.

Figure 6: Percentage distribution of tornadoes in months of the year in South America (1985-2018).

Source: The Authors.

Still according to the dates mentioned in the descriptions, the seasons of the year in which such events occurred were listed. It is worth noting that Venezuela and most of Colombia have territory in the Northern Hemisphere and therefore the seasons are the opposite of the Southern Hemisphere. Once the differential points were correct, the cases were grouped according to the seasons of the year, Figure (7).

Spring is the preferred season for tornado occurrences in South America (38%), similar to what happens in the United States (Tornado Alley).

Mainly in spring and summer, clouds of great vertical development occur, such as Cumulonimbus (Cbs), responsible for large amounts of rain, lightning, hail, windstorms and, eventually, tornadoes.

With the location data (local, city or municipality, state and country), it was possible to plot the points of occurrence of tornadoes in South America on a map (Figure 8) and relate them to the Enhanced Fujita Scale (EF).

Tornado events with very discrepant and/or insufficient information were considered “Unsortedtion”. It can be seen from this map that there are two large areas of occurrence, one in Southeast South America, as demonstrated by [16] but the novelty is a second region on the coast of the Caribbean Sea, north of Venezuela and Colombia, conditioned by the dynamics of tropical storms, most associated with the passage of hurricanes in the region [18].

Figure 7: Tornadoes by season in South America (1985-2018).

Source: The Authors.

The five highest frequency locations of tornado events from 1985 to 2018 were: the region of Campinas (8X), Barranquilla (7X), Florianópolis (5X), São Joaquim (4X) and Xanxerê (4X), Figure (9).

Each case was also analyzed individually according to the number of citations of authors. According to the literature, more impactful cases tend to have more studies with different purposes. From the data, the five most cited events were the cases of Xanxerê on May 20st 2015 (19), Indaiatuba on May 24st 2005 (12), Taquarituba on September 22st 2013 (7), Muitos Capões on August 30st 2005 (7) and Itu on September 30th 1991 (5), all in Brazil. These were also some of the most filmed by amateurs and studied by meteorologists, geographers, engineers and psychologists.

Figure 8: Spatialization of tornadoes in South America (from 1985-2018), using ArcGIS 10.3.

Source: Balicki, M. and Deobati, T.

Figure 9: Spatialization, concentration and frequency of tornadoes, using Software Surfer 13.

Source: The Authors.

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For the study period, in the summary of all events, the total number of injuries was 2,036 and deaths were 130 people. Therefore, finally, the 10 most violent tornadoes in South America were listed. As there cannot be anything more violent than death, the classification first followed the number of deaths, followed by the number of injuries, and finally, the Enhanced Fujita Scale (EF).

Only the 10 most violent tornadoes in South America caused a total of 95 deaths as a direct result of these events, and at least 1,156 injured from the years 1985 to 2018. Of these events, 5 occurred in autumn, 3 in spring and 2 in the winter. None in the summer.

The EF scale is all about levels of damage done. As shown in the table 1, two of the top three are EF-2s, considered intermediate in terms of strength, but which left more deaths than the other EF-4s that followed. That said, it is observed that the case of Pozo Del Tigre in Argentina, despite being considered EF-1, left more injured than that of Xanxerê (Brazil), considered EF-3. Itu in Brazil (EF-2) had more deaths than San Pedro in Argentina, which was considered an EF-4. In this case, we can also analyze that the passage over concentrated urban areas of the affected places as a preponderant factor (Table 1).

Table 1: Top 10 most violent tornadoes in South America (From 1985 to 2018).

Place:	Data:	Deaths:	Injured:	EF-Scale:
Buenos Aires - ARG	04/04/2012	26	200	EF-2
Ivinhema - BRA	29/07/1989	17	72	?
Itu - BRA	30/09/1991	15	176	EF-2
San Pedro - ARG	07/09/2009	10	40	EF-4
Almirante Tamandaré - BRA	17/05/1992	6	33	?
Antônio Prado - BRA	11/12/2003	5	12	EF-2
Dolores - URU	15/04/2016	4	250	EF-4
Pozo Del Tigre - ARG	21/10/2010	4	200	EF-1
Xanxerê - BRA	20/04/2015	4	97	EF-3
Nova Laranjeiras - BRA	13/06/1997	4	76	EF-3
Total		95	1.156	

Source: Compiled from articles cited in Google Scholar. (?) No information.

Of the 10 most violent tornadoes mentioned in the table 1, the cases of Xanxerê in Brazil in 2015 and Dolores in Uruguay in 2016, were studied and confirmed by national meteorological agencies such as INMET for Xanxerê [12] and INUMET for Dolores [13]. In addition, these were filmed from different angles and published in the media and social networks.

The Xanxerê (EF-3) and Dolores (EF-4) tornadoes occurred in April, autumn in the Southern Hemisphere, when the successive advance of Cold Fronts precedes the arrival of winter, moreover, they occurred in the mid-afternoon period, as cited by [9] on maturation the stage of development of Cumulonimbus (Cbs).

The two cases occurred in the southeastern region of South America and alerts were not issued for both, if that were the case, it is likely that the number of deaths and injuries would be minimized.

In view of the wide availability of cameras attached to cell phones and with radar images, it is easier to differentiate these events from downburst events, however, in view of the constant Fake News, it is still relevant to carry out a field study and reconnaissance of the area to better prove it the damage and the type of event that occurred, so as not to pollute the statistics and not generate unnecessary panic in the population. This technological availability associated with a large number of studies will bring more clarity to the dynamics of these phenomena in South America over time.

According [5, 6, 26] the greatest danger would occur in large urbanized areas. Thus, we can list cities like Buenos Aires, Assunción, Curitiba, Porto Alegre, Cascavel, Joinville, Florianópolis, Maringá, Londrina, Toledo, Foz do Iguazu, Sorocaba, Chapecó, Guarulhos, Campinas and especially the region of São Paulo city, since tornadoes of higher categories such as EF-3, and mainly EF-4 or EF-5 could cause hundreds of fatalities, mainly during the night.

The damage caused by tornadoes is closely related to the strength of the gusts of their winds, however, when they tend to pass through urban areas, they are able to carry and lift lighter objects and throw them like “missiles” against other buildings, or even in people or and animals. This is true when we verify events at different scales, such as the EF-4 in Dolores (Uruguay) and the EF-1 in Marechal Cândido Rondon (Brazil).

Despite the two cities being hit by tornadoes, the damage levels do not present similar appearances, obviously resulting from the intensity in the respective EF scale. Nor did the number of deaths (4 and 0, respectively) and injuries (250 and 23), however, the economic damage was close (US\$ 35 millions).

This is why the EF scale should be used as an estimate, as the damage is related to other factors, such as the amount of more fragile and lighter elements to be carried by the force of the winds, especially when passing through urbanized areas.

5. Conclusions

In South America, tornadoes are occasional, with two large regions of occurrence, but in smaller numbers compared to North America. After plotting the events on the map (Figure 8), two preferred regions became evident in South America, the southeast, comprising northern Argentina, Paraguay, Uruguay and south-central Brazil [6] and the coastal region of Colombia and Venezuela, close to the Caribbean Sea [21, 24].

The other regions of South America have a very low probability, but they are possible, such as events that occur along the Amazon basin, and cities close to the coast, with events that transform from waterspouts to weak tornadoes, when into the continent.

In southeastern South America they are commonly associated with the encounter of air masses of different characteristics over this region. To the North (Colombia and Venezuela) related to the passage of tropical storms over the Caribbean Sea.

Many venues have witnessed this type of event more than once in a 34-years period. Individually, Brazil is the third country in the world in number of tornadoes, behind only the United States and Canada. Weaker tornado events (EF-0 and EF-1) are the most common. However, disregarding these phenomena is dangerous, as these events are possible in many areas, such as the regions shown.

A large number of tornadoes did not have enough information for classification on the EF scale, in a total of 168, and most of the tornadoes presented, mainly in the central region of Brazil, are lands pout types that are weaker than those related to mesocyclone variants.

It is also noticeable that these phenomena apparently have a tendency to pass over populated areas, possibly related to the effect of urban heat islands associated with updrafts during the Cumulonimbus stage, usually with a mid-afternoon inversion. Obviously, tornadoes with longer tracks are more likely to pass through more densely populated areas (urban areas, villages and

communities) and, proportionally to speed, there is a considerable increase in injuries and deaths.

The low demographic density of some regions and the difficulty of classification make it difficult to correctly record these types of phenomena.

By the figures presented, the whole of South America has reported fewer tornadoes than Canada and Europe in recent years, but it should be noted that there must be a significantly greater number of tornadoes in regions of Chile, southern Bolivia, throughout the Uruguay, Paraguay and mainly in the North of Argentina and which have not gained the importance that they should have by researchers.

Episodes such as Nova Laranjeiras, Xanxerê and Dolores occurred in years of strong El Niño's trees further studies are needed.

More studies are needed to better understand "how" and "where" tornadoes act in South America. It is suggested that many case studies be made by Meteorology, Physics, Geography, Engineering and other areas so that, over time, these phenomena that are hidden even from science can be better identified and recognized.

This is important so that residents and governments can take more effective measures in order to minimize the impacts and prepare the population of these places.

6. List of Symbols and Acronyms

ARG – Argentina;

BRA – Brazil;

EF - Enhanced Fujita Scale;

URU – Uruguay;

USA – United States of America.

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